

Research Article

Bard G

Shirley Ling Jen^{1,*}, and Abdul Rahim Salam²

¹ Faculty of Educational Sciences & Technology, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia; lingjen81@yahoo.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4363-5690>)

² Language Academy, Faculty of Social Sciences & Humanities, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia; m-arahim@utm.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8023-1014>)

* Correspondence: lingjen81@yahoo.com; 013-7687397.

Abstract: *Essay writing has been a problem for Malaysian students as English is a second and even a third language for majority of our students. Since students nowadays are digital nomads, there is a need to use a more creative approach in teaching essay writing. One of them is through the use of Generative AI such as ChatGPT, Gemini and Copilot. Although artificial intelligence has been used by teachers and students, there is no proper guidelines in using it. Many teachers and students are still struggling to use AI for their daily activities. Thus, Bard G is a teaching technique developed by the researchers in guiding students to use Gemini AI in their essay writing. Bard G consists of a short video, two modules and a rainbow chart. In this study, 40 Form 3 students were chosen as respondents for this study. Based on Bard G, students can use Gemini easily without much guidance from teacher. Bard G consists of prompts, illustrations and step-by step explanations on how to use Gemini for essay writing. The T-test conducted on the use of Bard G in students' essay writing shows that students had improved significantly through the use of Bard G. On top of that, students had also showed favourable responses towards the use of Bard G in assisting them in using Gemini for their essay writing. Finally, the use of Bard G enables students to learn essay writing using Gemini AI easily and in an interesting way.*

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Student-centred learning; Second language acquisition.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Writing is one of the most difficult language skills to acquire because writing consists of many elements such as word choice, language use and spelling (Siddek & Ismail, 2021; Minn et al. 2019 and Rahman et al., 2020). The main problems faced by students in their essay writing include the inability to form grammatically accurate sentences and generalization of ideas due to poor command of vocabulary and interference from their mother tongue (Siddek & Ismail, 2021). Due to lack of time, lack of facilities and poor command of the English language, majority of our English teachers usually employ teacher-centred method in teaching essay writing (Gustiani, 2020 and Chun & Yunus, 2023). Thus, there should be a call for a more creative approach in teaching essay writing such as through the use of Artificial Intelligence (Alharbi 2023; Buriak et al; Quintans-Junior et al. and Kim, 2023).

Although AI has long existed since 1950, it has only made tremendous impact in education field since the emergence of ChatGPT. Similar to ChatGPT, Gemini is able to generalise information from a large corpus of data built in it. Research shows that Gemini can help with creative tasks, explaining complex topics and generally extracting information from a variety of sources on the internet.

Although studies had been carried out about ChatGPT, there are a few studies on the use of other AI tools especially among secondary school students (Aydın & Karaarslan, 2022; Jen & Salam, 2024; Rahman et al., 2023; and Libório et al., 2023). Moreover, there is lack of guidance in using AI such as Gemini. Thus, this has discouraged teachers and students to explore further in the field of AI.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

In this study, Bard G is a teaching technique developed in guiding students to use Gemini AI for essay writing. It consists of a short video, two modules and a rainbow chart. The first book is for beginner. It consists of explanation and illustrations about Gemini while the second book consists of step-by-step explanation in guiding students to use Gemini in all the three stages of essay writing: Pre-writing, while writing and post-writing. The second book also consists of translation in Bahasa Melayu to guide the weaker students in using Gemini for essay writing. In addition, the rainbow chart is developed to guide students to use Gemini more easily and in a faster way. It consists of only the prompts used in the three stages of essay writing. Below is the rainbow chart used in this study.

Figure 1: Rainbow Chart

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Findings from T-Test

40 students of a secondary school in Johor Bahru were chosen as the respondents to examine the effectiveness of Bard G in improving students' essay writing skills. A paired sample t-test was conducted to compare the pre-test and post test scores of the experimental group. The experimental group was the students who went through the essay writing class using Bard G. The results revealed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results as the p-value was less than 0.05. These findings suggest that we have to reject the null hypotheses as students had improved significantly through the use of Bard G in their essay writing.

3.2 Findings from Students' Journal Entries

All the 40 students were asked to write down their perceptions regarding the use of Bard G after the essay writing lessons. Below are the students' responses analysed using thematic approach.

- Student 1: With Bard G, we can use AI easily.
- Student 3: We can learn new words through Bard G.
- Student 4: Bard G is easy to use even for a 10-year-old kid.

3.3 Findings from Questionnaires

The questionnaires administered to the respondents in the study showed that all of them expressed that they liked using Bard G. This is because Bard G was easy to use. Apart from that, 95% of the students stated that they had improved their essay writing using Bard G and all of them stated that they had learnt new vocabulary and ideas from Bard G. This was termed as 'perceived usefulness' in the TAM Theory. Venkatesh et al (2003) asserted that, perceived usefulness is defined as the extent to which using a system enhances an individual's productivity. Bard G does not only help students in using Gemini easily, but generation of ideas, but also helps them to translate words from their mother tongue into suitable words in their essay writing.

3.4 Findings from Observation

It was observed that all the students could learn how to use Gemini easily using Bard G. They even ventured further on their own by using Gemini for their other writing tasks. However, it was observed that not all the students were given equal opportunities in using Gemini and time was limited for students to explore using Gemini. To overcome this problem, students were asked to continue surfing for online materials using Gemini at home since most of them had either mobile phones or laptops at home.

3.5 Findings from Semi-Structured Interview

The focus group interviews conducted with the students showed that all of them liked to use Bard G. This was because Bard G was something new for them. Bard G also has many other benefits as highlighted by the students.

Firstly, Bard G helped students to know the appropriate way to generate ideas for their essays using Gemini. Students were only required to enter the keywords into the 'prompt' for the essay task and Gemini would generate a lot of content in paragraphs for them. Apart from that, students had also improved their vocabulary as students could key in words in their mother tongue into the system. Gemini would then translate the given word into a few suggested English words with explanation. Through this, students had not only learnt about the new words, but they had also learnt the meaning of the new words provided by Gemini. Finally, Gemini had also improved students' reading comprehension and pronunciation through the 'Read Along' feature provided in the text. Once activated, the 'Read Along' feature in Gemini would read out all the words shown in the Gemini. Students would be able to learn about the correct pronunciation of every word and at the same time understood the text better since they were not only using their sight sensory but they were using their listening sensory at the same time.

Finally, all the students stated that they did not face any problem while using Gemini. This is because Bard G provided step-by-step guidance in using Gemini. Students were only required to key in the keywords into the 'prompt' function as shown in the rainbow chart and the responses would be given by Gemini in a split second. Thus, students did not face any problem while using Bard G. This

'perceived ease of use' feature of Bard G enables it to be used easily and conveniently (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Bard G is a great aid for students in using Gemini to improve their writing performance. This is supported by studies done by Guo et al. (2022) and Nazari et al. (2021) who asserted that Artificial Intelligence tools have great benefits in improving students' essay writing performance. This is because apart from generating ideas, Artificial Intelligence tools are also able to perform other functions such as translation, providing feedback, evaluating students' essays and give personalised comments to the users. Future research should be carried out regarding the use of Bard G with different age groups apart from Form 3 students.

References

- Alharbi, W. (2023). The use and abuse of artificial intelligence-enabled machine translation in the EFL classroom: An exploratory study. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 10(4), 689-701.
- Aydın, Ö., Karaarslan, E.(2022). OpenAI ChatGPT generated literature review: Digital twin in healthcare. In Ö. Aydın (Ed.), *Emerging Computer Technologies*, 2.
- Buriak, J. M., Akinwande, D., Artzi, N., Brinker, C. J., Burrows, C., Chan, W. C., ... & Ye, J. (2023). Best practices for using AI when writing scientific manuscripts: Caution, care, and consideration: Creative science depends on it. *ACS Nano*, 17(5), 4091- 4093.
- Chun, T. W., & Yunus, M. M. (2023). Factors affecting Malaysian ESL teachers' behavioral intentions for technology use in the post-COVID-19 era. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1127272.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 319-340.
- Guo, K., Wang, J., & Chu, S. K. W. (2022). Using Chatbots to scaffold EFL students' argumentative writing. *Assessing Writing*, 54,100666.
- Gustiani, S. (2020). Students' motivation in online learning during COVID-19 pandemic era: A case study. *Holistics (Hospitality and Linguistics): Jurnal Ilmiah Bahasa Inggris*, 12(2).
- Jen, S. L., & Salam, A. R. H. (2024). Using Bard to improve secondary school students' essay writing performance. *Journal of Creative Practices in Language Learning and Teaching (CPLT)*, 12(1).
- K. S. S. Menengah (2000). *Bahasa Inggeris*. Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia.
- Kim, S. G. (2023). Using ChatGPT for language editing in scientific articles. *Maxillofacial Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 45(1), 13.
- Libório, M. P., Martins, C. A. P., Laudares, S., & Ekel, P. I. (2023). Method of preparing an international and national literature review for novice researchers. *MethodsX*, 10, 102165.
- Miin, W. P., Rou, L. Y., & Yunus, M. M. (2019). Google Docs: Step by step sentence construction for primary school marginal passing rate pupils. *Creative Education*, 10(02), 237.<https://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ce.2019.102019>.
- Nazari, N., Shabbir, M. S., & Setiawan, R. (2021). Application of artificial intelligence powered digital writing assistant in higher education: Randomized controlled trial. *Heliyon*, 7(5).
- Quintans-Júnior, L. J., Gurgel, R. Q., Araújo, A. A. D. S., Correia, D., & Martins-Filho, P. R. (2023). ChatGPT: The new panacea of the academic world. *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical*, 56, e0060-2023.

- Rahman, A. M. A., Azmi, M. N. L., & Hassan, I. (2020). Improvement of English writing skills through blended learning among university students in Malaysia. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(12A), 7694701. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.082556>
- Rahman, M. M., Terano, H. J., Rahman, M. N., Salamzadeh, A., & Rahaman, M. S. (2023). ChatGPT and academic research: A review and recommendations based on practical examples. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 3(1), 1-12.
- Siddek, N. A. J., & Ismail, H. H. (2021). Understanding learners' difficulties in narrative writing among Malaysian primary learners. *Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 3(2), 244-255.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 425-478.